

ISic0818

I.Sicily inscription 0818

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (local)

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Noto, Biblioteca comunale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644907

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1964.0157

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique.* At 1964.0627

Manganaro, G. 1962. Graffiti e iscrizioni funerarie della Sicilia orientale. *Helikon.* 2: 485-501. At fig.3-4

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